

Gesture-Controlled Smart Computing for Home Automation

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Abstract—This article proposes a smart computing system for home automation that leverages gesture recognition via the Internet of Things (IoT). The focus is on the inclusion of deaf individuals, eliminating the need for voice commands. To enable this smart computing, a free platform, Teachable Machine, was used to train a machine learning-based model. Data from the gestures recognized by the model were stored in a cloud database using a free tool developed by the authors, called FMIoT. This data was then accessed by an ESP32 microcontroller to activate an electronic device, demonstrating a practical application of smart computing in automation. FMIoT allows for the creation of a customized website with webcam access, which serves as an interface between the Teachable Machine model and the database accessed by the ESP32. The results showed 100% precision in recognizing the programmed gestures, proving the efficiency of this smart computing method as an accessible solution for IoT-based home automation systems.

Index Terms—Accessibility and Inclusion, Gesture Recognition, Home Automation, Internet of Things, Machine Learning, Smart Computing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) connects everyday objects to the Internet, bridging physical and virtual spaces through advancements in networking technologies. In this context, smart computing emerges as a crucial paradigm, merging hardware, software, and networking to provide systems with real-time monitoring [1]. Unlike traditional computing, which merely processes tasks, smart computing leverages technologies like the IoT, artificial intelligence (AI), and machine learning to analyze data, make intelligent decisions, and act automatically. It is the core concept behind intelligent devices, enabling a seamless cycle of sensing, analyzing, and acting for more efficient and responsive systems [2].

Currently, AI-powered virtual assistants perform home automation tasks using cloud-based voice commands [3]. These systems rely on Machine Learning (ML), which identifies patterns in data to enable decision-making with minimal human intervention [4]. While ML involves complex mathematical processes, platforms like Teachable Machine democratize this technology, allowing users to create machine learning models quickly and intuitively without requiring deep technical knowledge [5].

Despite these advancements, efficient smart computing systems that are truly inclusive of deaf individuals remain scarce. This is a critical need, especially in Brazil, where inclusive IoT projects are limited due to historical educational segregation and restricted access to advanced technologies [6]. Gesture-based systems present a promising alternative.

Manufacturers predict that gesture control will become as natural as voice commands, making technology more intuitive and accessible, particularly for the deaf community [7].

Previous efforts, such as the work of [8], successfully developed a gesture recognition system using a Raspberry Pi 3 B+ and Pi Camera, achieving 96.67% accuracy with the Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD) deep learning model [9]. Integration with Telegram allowed recognized symbols to be communicated effectively. To further improve real-time performance, expanding the image dataset to include varying environments and lighting conditions was recommended.

It is important to clarify the distinction between gestures and signs, noting that while signs from Brazilian Sign Language (Libras) are gestures, not all gestures are official signs. This is a key point, as relying solely on formal signs can be challenging for deaf individuals who don't use Libras or for people with speech impairments. The proposed system addresses this by using gestures to train an AI, creating a more inclusive solution for home automation. The text highlights how current market systems often depend on voice commands or limited sensor-based movements. In contrast, the authors' FMIoT system uses a single camera and a machine learning model to recognize various gestures, allowing for the control of multiple devices. The FMIoT platform acts as the bridge between the gesture recognition and the home automation hardware, storing the trained model in the cloud for real-time access and reliable performance.

II. METHODOLOGY

The following subsections detail the hardware and software used for the development of the proposed project.

A. ESP32

The Internet of Things (IoT) has gained prominence in automation by enabling remote control of environments via Wi-Fi, providing practicality, agility, and security. This makes IoT a powerful tool for fostering inclusion, particularly for individuals with disabilities.

The proposed project uses IoT to empower deaf individuals to manage daily activities through a gesture-based interface. To achieve this, the system integrates sensors and actuators using the ESP32 microcontroller, a widely adopted development platform created by Espressif Systems. The ESP32 stands out for its integrated Wi-Fi and Bluetooth modules, efficient processing, and low power consumption, making it ideal for IoT projects requiring Internet connectivity [10], [11].

The ESP32 includes a Dual-Core 32-bit LX6 processor and an Ultra-Low Power (ULP) coprocessor, which allows operation in Deep Sleep mode to conserve energy [12]. It operates at 3.3V DC with versatile GPIO pins, supporting digital, analog, and touch-sensitive configurations. Additional features include ADC/DAC converters, a Real-Time Clock (RTC), and PWM peripherals, enabling diverse automation tasks [13].

The ESP32's compatibility with the Arduino IDE further simplifies development, making it accessible to IoT project developers [12].

B. Protocols And Online Communication Tools

The Internet connection is fundamental to this project, enabling the ESP32 microcontroller to act as a Web Server that hosts a customizable website using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript. This website facilitates user interaction, allowing individuals—such as those with speech impairments—to control devices remotely via gestures. Communication occurs through optimized protocols like MQTT or Firebase.

The MQTT protocol offers efficient and secure publish/subscribe communication, where data is sent to a broker, which manages and distributes information to subscribers. Its low hardware demands and Quality of Service (QoS) levels make MQTT ideal for IoT applications, as it ensures reliable, encrypted communication even with limited bandwidth [14], [15].

Alternatively, Firebase simplifies development by providing a cloud-hosted back-end structure. It integrates with multiple programming languages (e.g., JavaScript, Java, and C++), offers real-time synchronization, authentication, and enhanced data security via cloud storage [16].

To overcome the challenges of web development for broader adoption, the project uses the FMIoT tool. FMIoT bridges communication between devices and users by integrating protocols like MQTT and Firebase, enabling gesture-based automation without advanced programming knowledge.

For gesture recognition, the project uses Teachable Machine, a platform that simplifies AI model training [17]. The user selects the "Standard Image Model", which supports high-quality, color images—ideal for recognizing gestures captured via a camera.

These tools collectively enable an accessible, user-friendly IoT system, enhancing home automation for individuals with specific needs.

Fig. 1. shows a schematic diagram of the communication with the proposed system.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the Teachable Machine tool, the gesture recognition process for training the proposed system was initiated. The results obtained are described below.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the proposed system communication.

The application differentiates groups of similar images using the concept of *Class*. In this project, each class corresponds to a specific gesture and is named using the *key-value model*, which involves assigning a key (the attribute to be modified) and a value (the new state of the attribute) [18].

Next, the default name "Class 1" must be replaced with "pin5_1". Following the key-value model, this nomenclature means that pin 5 of the microcontroller will assume a logical value of 1 (*high*) when the gesture associated with this class (open hand) is detected. To add gesture images, the user can click "Webcam" to capture new photos or "Upload" to upload pre-existing images. This process must be repeated for all necessary gestures.

Fig. 2 illustrates the classes already registered and ready for training. For the example proposed in this article, three classes were trained: "pin5_1", "pin5_0", and "pin5_nothing". The "pin5_nothing" class was added to ensure that the model can also identify the *absence of gestures*.

Once the configuration is complete, the model must be trained by clicking the "Train Model" button. It is important to note that the Teachable Machine tab should not be altered or closed during this process to ensure successful training. When the model is ready, the preview feature is enabled, allowing the model to be tested immediately. It can be observed in Fig. 3 that the open hand gesture is recognized by the "pin5_1" class with 100% accuracy, the same applies to the "pin5_0" class for the closed hand gesture, and finally, the "pin5_nothing" class recognizes 100% of the absence of gestures.

The tool also allows for the exportation of trained models to the cloud through an access URL generated by the website. This URL will later be used by the proposed FMIoT tool to classify gestures and trigger electronic devices through the ESP32 microcontroller.

With the machine learning model fully trained and available in the cloud, an interface between the artificial intelligence and the ESP32 is required. This is where FMIoT comes in. FMIoT is a website-based tool that allows the creation of

a profile incorporating the model generated by Teachable Machine to communicate the results to the microcontroller. After creating the profile (Fig. 4), FMIoT enables gesture recognition through a webcam and displays the model's prediction results in real-time [19].

At the same time, an Application Programming Interface (API) will be online and ready to communicate with the world [20]. An API, as the name suggests, is an interface that connects one system to others. Since this primary system communicates in a unique way, it would not be possible to extract data from it without this communication mechanism.

The communication mechanism is prepared using Firebase, a cloud-based toolset. The access link will depend on the name of the profile created in FMIoT. Using this URL, the final step is to create a firmware for the ESP32 that can communicate with the FMIoT API, extract its information, and reflect it on the microcontroller. For system testing purposes, the firmware will be created using the Wokwi emulator, which can simulate microcontrollers compatible with IoT. Once this programming is completed and loaded onto the microcontroller, the real effects of the application can be visualized through the simulator (Fig. 5).

Fig. 2. Class training using the Teachable Machine tool.

Fig. 3. Testing of the created classes.

Fig. 4. Profile creation using the proposed FMIoT tool.

Fig. 6 shows the customized website created, featuring a webcam interface for gesture detection and showing the successful detection of “pin5_1” Class, triggering the LED on the ESP32 in the simulator.

Fig. 5. Customized website generated by the FMIoT platform.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed project successfully demonstrates the feasibility of using gesture recognition combined with IoT technologies to enhance accessibility and inclusion, particularly for deaf individuals. By integrating tools such as Teachable

Fig. 6. Customized website generated by the FMIoT platform.

Machine for machine learning and the ESP32 microcontroller, the system bridges the gap between artificial intelligence and home automation.

The use of Firebase as a cloud communication platform and the FMIoT tool ensures efficient communication between the AI model and the hardware, enabling real-time gesture recognition and device activation. The simulation using Wokwi further validates the system's functionality, showcasing its potential in practical applications.

The proposed solution offers a significant step towards democratizing access to smart home automation technologies, fostering independence and improving the quality of life for individuals with hearing impairments. Future developments will focus on integrating official sign language gestures, expanding the gesture database, and improving the system's adaptability to various real-world environments. In summary, the FMIoT platform demonstrates the potential of IoT to drive inclusion through innovation, providing a practical and scalable solution for gesture-based home automation systems.

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